

Production tests of advanced screw conveyor and chain transmission for lint transportation

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Running title: Production tests of screw conveyor and chain transmission

Abstract: The article shows the transmission scheme of a screw with a wavy (zigzag) shape of the surface of rotation and chain transmission with a compound roller, as well as an analysis of their structural properties. The results of experimental studies conducted to determine the operability of a chain drive with a composite roller installed in the drive mechanism of a new-design screw conveyor are described. It also describes the process of cleaning small and large litter of various kinds from the composition of lint on a recommended design based on experimental results.

Development of an efficient structure of a screw conveyor that transports and cleans lint, and determines its parameters based on complex experimental studies.

Experimental studies were conducted at the Tashkent Research Institute of Mechanization and Electrification of Agriculture using the tensometric test method. Here, the angular velocities of the screw shaft are determined with the help of tensor resistors.

As a result of experimental studies, the laws of changing the angular speeds of the screw shaft and the leading star shaft of the fluff transportation and cleaning screw conveyor were determined in different working conditions. These laws were determined by the oscillograms presented in the article.

In the article, the laws of change of angular velocities on the screw and leading star shafts of the screw conveyor carrying and cleaning cotton lint were determined experimentally. Graphs of dependence of angular velocities and their vibration ranges on performance and wave height on the surface of the screw were constructed. Based on the analysis, the optimal values of the parameters were recommended.

Keywords: screw conveyor, chain transmission, roller, rubber, tray, mesh surface, cleaning, thermal moisture meter, scales.

Introduction.

Screw conveyors are widely used in the transportation of various materials, especially loose and fibrous materials. In the technological system of cotton processing, fluff is cleaned from external impurities using a screw cleaner. In an existing screw conveyor with a fixed conveyor, the movement of loads along the conveyor is carried out using rotating screws. In this construction, there is a possibility of jamming of the load in the conveyor during high energy consumption and transfer of large quantities of material. The noise will also be high.

In existing screw conveyors, the transportation of fibrous materials, especially fluff, produces less waste due to insufficient material separation. In addition, due to the lack of sufficient friction between the screw surface and the fiber material, it is observed that they stick during transportation, which causes additional mechanical damage to the fiber material, fluff. The interaction of the screw surface with fluff is carried out uniformly in one direction, with a constant driving force, which does not ensure their cleaning efficiency. The design of the screw conveyor was improved by increasing the contact area, increasing the friction force, as well as changing the values of the direction of interaction of the screw with the cotton wool being transported, in order to ensure sufficient vibration and shaking of the transported fibrous material, to increase the cleaning effect and the required transportation efficiency.

In order to overcome the above shortcomings, a fluff cleaner with a wavy surface was recommended [1]. Also, in order to reduce power consumption, reduce noise, and increase operational resources, a chain transmission conveyor was proposed.

a

b

Fig.1. An experimental view of a flexible element chain drive (b) mounted on a zigzag-shaped screw conveyor (a) of a new design that carries fluff from a linting machine

The screw conveyor contains a chute 1, the lower part of which has the shape of a half-cylinder, closed from above by a cover 2. Inside the chute 1, along its axis, a screw 3 transports material. At the top of the chute 1 there is an inlet 4, and at the end, at the bottom, there is an outlet 7. The lower working part gutter 1 is made in the form of a mesh surface 8. The working surfaces of the screw (coil) 3 are made in a zig-zig shape 5, having triangular protrusions and depressions. The height of the triangles 5 of the screw 3 is chosen equal to the average size of the cotton seed, (4.0÷7.0) mm. Ribs 6 of triangles 5 of the screw are mutually parallel and when wound onto the shaft they are directed along the radius of the screw 3.

Screw conveyor works as follows. Fibrous material (raw cotton, fibrous waste) is fed into the chute 1 through the inlet 7 in the cover 2 and, when the screw 3 rotates, it slides along the chute 1 dragged by the zigzag (triangular) working surface 5 of the rotating screw 3 to the outlet 8.

The zig-zag (triangular protrusions and depressions) 5 shape of the working surfaces of the screw 3 acts on the seeds and cotton buds with a force of different magnitude and direction, which leads to additional loosening of the cotton, this allows for the effective separation of litter from the fibrous material (cotton). Weed impurities isolated from the fibrous material fall out through the holes of the mesh surface 8 of the trough 1 and are discharged into the self-removal through the hole.

The essence of the recommended design is that the screw conveyor contains a fixed chute, the lower part of which has the shape of a half-cylinder, closed from above by a lid, and a drive screw installed inside the chute along its axis in bearings fixed on the chute. The lower working part of the gutter is made in the form of a mesh surface. The movement of the load along the chute is carried out by turns of the screw, the working surface of the turns of the screw is made in the form of an accordion, a zigzag shape (triangular protrusions and depressions), the height of which is chosen equal to the average size of the cotton fly seed, (4,0÷7,0) mm. This form of the working surface of the screw allows an increase in the contact area with the transported cotton (fibrous waste), the degree of loosening and the cleaning effect increase [2].

During the operation of the screw conveyor, fibrous material (raw cotton, fibrous waste) is fed into the chute through the inlet in the lid and, when the screw rotates, slides along the chute dragged by the zigzag (triangular) working surface of the rotating screw to the outlet.

The zigzag (triangular protrusions and depressions) shape of the working surfaces of the screw acts on the seeds and cotton bats with a force of different magnitude and direction, which leads to additional loosening of the cotton, this allows for the effective separation of litter from the fibrous material (cotton). Weed impurities isolated from the fibrous material fall out through the holes of the mesh surface of the gutter and are discharged into the self-removal through the hole.

The well-known design of the chain transmission contains a driving and driven sprockets and a flexible chain element that transmits movement from the driving sprocket to the driven one [3]. The disadvantage of this chain transmission is, in the process of operation, a decrease in the angle of wrapping of the chain of sprockets, a significant sagging of the driven (idle) branch of the chain, leading to a decrease in efficiency, and in some cases, breaking or disengaging the chain with sprockets [4]. In addition, when significant loads are transferred at high speeds, noise occurs and due to the impact interactions of the sprocket teeth with the surfaces of the chain rollers, friction increases, thereby causing wear of both the chain rollers and the sprocket teeth.

The chains used in mechanical engineering are divided into three main groups according to the nature of the work they perform: drive, traction and cargo. Drive chains are the most common. They transmit movement from the energy source to the receiving organ of the machine; work both at low and high speeds (up to 30-35m/s) and at different distances between the axes (centers) of the sprockets. One chain can drive several at the same time. In almost all types of chain design, noise occurs in gears due to impact interactions of the sprocket teeth with the surfaces of the chain rollers, and friction also increases, thereby causing wear of both the chain rollers and the sprocket teeth [5]. To increase the reliability of operation and the life of the chain transmission, the design of the transmission chain has been improved using elastic elements.

The design of the chain transmission includes a drive 1 and a driven sprocket 2, a chain 3 covering them, a tension roller 4. The driven sprocket 2 is made composite consisting of an outer part 2 with teeth, a base 6 with an output shaft 7, an elastic annular sleeve 5 (Fig.). Chain 3 includes outer 8 and inner 9 links, roller 10, bushing 11 and composite roller 12, consisting of outer 13 and inner 14 bushings, between which a rubber (elastic) bushing 15 is installed. The outer surface 16 of the rubber bushing 15 is made of a concave curvilinear shape, respectively the inner surface of the outer sleeve 8 is made of a curved convex shape.

Rubber bushings protrude from the recesses of the ring bushings (Fig. 1b). The new waveform design of the screw conveyor is shown in Fig. 2b. Figure 2 shows a view of the constructions produced on the basis of the invention patents IAP 06200 and IAP 06472 [6,7].

a

b

Fig.2. An experimental version of a newly constructed corrugated screw mounted on a pressing shop and a chain drive of a newly constructed flexible element:

- a) chain drive with a new design flexible element**
- b) new design corrugated (zig-zag) surface screw conveyor**

Results.

The fluff carrier from the linter machine is subjected to various forces due to the new design screw conveyor and the replacement of the coupling in the drive mechanism with a composite roller chain, and as a result of the normal operation of the screw conveyor, the corrugated screw surface collides with the fluff.

It also grinds to a certain extent by interacting with the surface of the transported screw under certain angles in the form of a wave. In this process, fine wastes are separated between the feathers, which are mixed with different strength. As a result, the various contaminants in the fluff are effectively separated and drained down through the mesh surface.

Determining the high performance of a new experimental copy of a new design corrugated screw and a flexible element chain drive from a linter machine mounted on a pressing shop depends on determining the efficiency of transportation.

The effectiveness of the cleaning of fluff carried in the existing and recommended constructions in the laboratory by a special method was determined. The moisture content of the samples was measured and 50 grams of lint was removed. Then the entire seed, kojitsa, contained in the fluff was separated. The remaining lint was sifted through a laboratory sieve. In the next process, small impurities and fluff were separated. Separated kojittsa, fluff, small impurities were weighed separately. At the end, the fluff separated from the impurities was weighed again (Fig. 3).

Fig.3. The process of determining the quality of refined wool in the laboratory by passing the recommended constructions

Experiments were conducted on the second and third varieties of Andijan-35 selection variety (Table 1).

The results of a comparative test of the variants mounted on a screw conveyor with a chain drive (available in series) with a chain drive mounted on the working bushing through the rubber bushings of the ring outer bushings with the recommended composition roller are given in Table 2. Based on the analysis of Table 2, it was determined that the recommended chain extension performance is high.

Based on the figures in Table 1, it was found that if the available chain extension resource is 1,0, the extension working resource with the recommended flexible element chain will increase by 1,25 or 25%.

In chain extensions, friction is created due to sliding, i.e. the chain length increases. It was found that the relative elongation of the chain segment in the existing chain extension was 2,5%, while the elongation of the chain segment in the proposed chain extension was 4,0 times less, 0,6%. This is mainly due to the fact that when the chain roller engages with the sprocket teeth, the force is damped because it is a rubber bushing. This reduces friction. This means that the elongation is reduced and the chain elongation is reduced. It was found that the relative elongation of the chain section increases with time, i.e., the shear rate is 3,0 times lower than the available elongation in the recommended chain extension [8].

Stops were detected in the process machines due to the fact that the chain deviated from the star, interrupted and increased noise as the technological load and operating mode increased. While the existing series of chain extensions detected 11 stops at 120 hours of operation, there were no stops when an extension with the recommended flexible element chain was used. It was found that the noise

was reduced by 2,5÷2,8 times compared to the existing extension when the recommended chain extension was used [9].

It was found that the new design corrugated (zig-zag) screw mounted on the conveyor screw conveyor in the pressing shop and the experimental copy of the chain drive of the flexible element have a high ability to process in the test process.

№	cotton type	sort	humidity	weight	Screw conveyor available							Newly designed screw conveyor							Cleaning efficiency in transport.			
					whole seed	fluff	skin	minor pollution	waste	total pollution	Lint residue	whole sed	fluff	skin	minor pollution	waste	total pollution	lint resid.	gram	%		
1	Andijon-35	2	6,7	50	0,1	1,8	1,44	1,85	0,07	5,26	44,74	89,48%	0,06	0,68	0,65	0,46	0,03	1,88	48,12	96,24%	3,38	6,76%
2	Andijon-35	3	7,2	50	0,18	2,4	1,96	2,25	0,17	6,96	43,04	86,08%	0,08	0,82	1,12	0,77	0,07	2,86	47,14	94,28%	4,1	8,20%

Table 1. Experiment results.

№	Name of indicators	Available chain extension	An extension with a recommended elastic element chain
1	Relative elongation of the chain part, %	2,5	0,6
2	The rate of erosion, % / hour	0,045	0,015
3	Number of stops, (120 hours)	9	0
4	Noise, Db $v = (2,5 \div 3,5) \text{ m / s}$	25÷30	10÷12
5	Relative resource	1,0	1,25

Table 2. Chain parameters.

Discussions.

According to the results obtained, the recommended screw surface corrugated (zig-zag) design and the use of flexible element chain extensions reduce the amount of contaminants in the fluff compared to the existing design, and the cleaning efficiency during transportation depends on the fluff varieties 6,76% from 8,20% [10].

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Conclusion:

According to the results of the comparative production test of the recommended fluff-carrying and cleaning improved wavy-surfaced screw conveyor and chain drive with a belt element in the driver, the amount of various types of impurities in the fluff content is reduced compared to the existing structure, and the cleaning efficiency during the transportation process is 6.76% to 8.20% depending on the fluff varieties. showed an increase of %, the conveyor resource increased by 25%, the chain roll decreased by 3 times, the noise decreased by 2.8 times.

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